

Mean annual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{sw}}$

$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{sw}}$ seasonality

Higher offset
↑
↓
Lower offset

Mean annual SST

SST seasonality

Legend to case types

- Control
- Variability in record length
- Variability in age model uncertainty
- Variability in growth rate
- Variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{sw}}$
- Variability in SST
- Variability in growth rate and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{sw}}$
- Variability in growth rate, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{sw}}$ and SST